

Repositories and Archiving

Tip 1: Investigate Different Types of Repositories

**First Choice:
A Trusted
Discipline Specific
Repository**

**Second Choice:
An Institutional
Repository**

**Third Choice:
A General
Non-Institutional
Repository**

Tip 2: Know some Repository Basics.

Why use an Repository?

Using an archives ensures that your research outputs are safely stored long-term, are findable by other researchers, and are reusable.

How to Find an Repository

You can use tools like re3data.org to search for discipline specific repository. Look for options that are certified or that are frequently used in your field of study. You can also review the published literature to view how others manage their data.

PHAIDRA: The University's Repository

If you cannot find suitable discipline specific repositories for all your data, the univie repository, [PHAIDRA](https://phaidra.univie.ac.at), is always here for you!

Preparing Data for Archiving

1. Review the repository's submission process and guidelines early.
2. Be aware of any costs associated with upload. Not all repositories are free to use.
3. Learn about the repository's metadata standards. If no discipline specific guidelines are provided, decide what metadata you will include.
4. Be prepared to select licenses for your outputs. Always assign a license and ensure your selection is appropriate for the type of object you have produced.
5. Do not be afraid to contact the repository to ask questions or request assistance.

RDM Homepage

How to Reach the RDM Team

Anyone at univie can reach-out to the RDM team for help. You can reach us at rdm@univie.ac.at or find our webpage at rdm.univie.ac.at.